

Modern Friedel-Crafts chemistry. Part-27¹. Alkylation of benzene with 1-benzyl- and 1-phenylcyclohexanols in the presence of H₂SO₄ and AlCl₃/CH₃NO₂ catalysts

Ali A. Khalaf*, Ibrahim M. Awad, Talaat I. El-Emary and Hassan A. K. Abd El-Aal

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Assiut University, Assiut, Egypt

E-mail : prof_khalaf@hotmail.com

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Abstract : The alkylation of benzyene with 1-benzylcyclohexanol (3) gave a mixture of 2,3-benzobicyclo[3.3.1]nona-2-ene (8, 79%) and cyclohexyldiphenylmethane (10, 21%) with AlCl₃/CH₃NO₂ catalyst and a mixture of 1-benzylcyclohexene 5 (47.5%), 8 (8%), 10 (21.5%), 1-cyclopentyl-1,2-diphenylethane (12, 18%) and 1-benzyl-1-phenylcyclohexene (13, 4%) with H₂SO₄ catalyst. Treatment of 3 with AlCl₃/CH₃NO₂ in petroleum ether gave a mixture of 5 (26%) and 8 (62%). Attempted alkylation of benzene with 1-phenylcyclohexanol (4) in the presence of either AlCl₃/CH₃NO₂ or H₂SO₄ catalyst gave 1-(1-phenylcyclohexyl)-2-phenylcyclohexene (17) as sole product. Mechanistic interpretation of the results in terms of carbocation behaviour is offered.

Keywords : Friedal-Crafts chemistry, alkylation, 1-benzylcyclohexanol, 1-phenylcyclohexanol, AlCl₃ catalyst.

In previous papers of this series^{1,2}, we reported that compounds 1 and 2 were obtained as almost sole products from the respective AlCl₃/CH₃NO₂-catalysed alkylations of benzene and isobutylbenzene with 1-methylcyclohexanol following standard procedures³. In this paper we report our related results on the alkylation of benzene with 1-benzyl- and 1-phenylcyclohexanols 3 and 4, respectively in the presence of AlCl₃/CH₃NO₂ and H₂SO₄ catalysts.

Results and discussion

Synthesis of alkylating cyclohexanols : The starting 1-benzylcyclohexanol (3)⁴ and 1-phenylcyclohexanol (4)⁵ are known and were repeatedly obtained by the reaction of cyclohexanone with various organometallic reagents. In this work, the Grignard method formulated below was chosen to obtain 3 and 4 but with significant experimental modifications to improve the yields.

Alkylation of benzene with benzylcyclohexanol (3)⁴ : The alkylation of benzene with 3 was attempted using both AlCl₃/CH₃NO₂ and H₂SO₄ catalysts. Combined

chromatographic (TLC, GC, GC-MS), spectral (IR, ¹H NMR) and elemental analyses of the product showed that (Scheme 1) with AlCl₃/CH₃NO₂ catalyst, the product consisted of 2,3-benzobicyclo[3.3.1]nona-2-ene (8, 79.01%) and cyclohexyldiphenylmethane (10, 20.98%). With H₂SO₄ catalyst, however, the product was more complex consisting of five components. These were shown to be 1-benzylcyclohexene 5 (47.39%), 8 (8.18%), 10 (21.47%), 1-cyclopentyl-1,2-diphenylmethane 12 (17.69%) and 1-benzyl-1-phenylcyclohexene 13 (3.52%).

Commenting on Scheme 1, the following points are to be emphasised : (i) The identities of compounds 5 and 8 were further confirmed by unequivocal syntheses as well as by comparison with literature data⁶. (ii) The formation of 8 through the route 3 → 4 → 6 → 7 → 8 received experimental support from the finding that treatment of 3 with AlCl₃/CH₃NO₂ in petroleum ether solvent under comparable reaction conditions gave a hydrocarbon mixture consisting of intermediate cyclohexene 5 (25.62%),

Scheme 1

bridgehead **8** (62.31%) and a dimer of **5** (**14**, 10.6%). This dimer whose exact structure was not yet determined showed a parent M⁺ peak at *m/z* 344 corresponding to molecular formula C₂₆H₃₂. (iii) The structure of compound **12** was based practically on its MS data which showed a parent M⁺ peak at *m/z* 250 and a base peak at *m/z* 181 corresponding to the loss of a cyclopentyl C₅H₉ fragment⁷.

Theoretically, the formation of **12** via **6** → **5** ring contraction receives sound support from considerable literature reports^{8,9}.

Attempted alkylation of benzene with 1-phenylcyclohexanol (4) : The alkylation of benzene with **4** was attempted in the presence of AlCl₃/CH₃NO₂ and H₂SO₄ catalyst. None of the direct alkylation products were produced in either case. Instead, a hydrocarbon whose mass spectrum showed a parent M⁺ peak at *m/z* 216 corresponding to a molecular formula of C₂₄H₂₈. This formula suggested a dimer which on theoretical grounds could be either the 1-(1-phenylcyclohexyl)-2-phenylcyclohexene (**17**) or the spiro compound **18** as shown in Scheme 2.

The practical observations that : (a) the product discharged the colour of KMnO₄-acetone solution, (b) gave benzoic acid on oxidation with conc. nitric acid, (c) showed

Scheme 2

a C=C band at 1590 cm⁻¹ in the IR spectrum, (d) showed a ratio of aromatic to aliphatic protons of 10 to 18 in the ¹H NMR spectrum and (e) its MS showed a correct molecular ion at *m/z* 316 (51.5%) and fragments at *m/z* 159.1

(2.3%) for phenylcyclohexyl and at m/z 157.8 (1.8%) for phenylcyclohexenyl suggested **17** to be the structure of choice ruling out structure **18**.

The results of Scheme 2 deserves to be rationalised. First, the failure to obtain any diphenylcyclohexene alkylate is probably due to combined electronic and steric reasons. While electronic factors favoured the localisation of the positive charge at the tertiary benzylic center, steric constrains hindered phenylation at the same center. Second, the preference for the endocyclic elimination to give **17** over ring closure to give **18** stems again from inhibiting steric interactions operating at the closure step under the employed reaction conditions.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected and were determined on a Gallenkamp electric m.p. apparatus using open capillary tubes. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian EM-360 60 MHz, a Varian EM-390 90 MHz or a JEOL JNM-LA400 400 MHz spectrometer. IR spectra were recorded on a Shimadzo 470 IR spectrometer. MS spectra were recorded on a JEOL JMS-600 spectrometer and GC/MS data were recorded on a GC-Hewlett Packard connected with JWS 600H using direct inlet system. Thin layer chromatography (TLC) was performed using 5×15 cm glass plates coated with a thin film of silica gel (60 mesh). Preparative TLC was performed using 20×20 cm plates coated with a thick film of silica gel (60 mesh). Column chromatography (CC) was carried out using a 1×25 cm column packed with either alumina or silica gel (30 g per 1g of organic material). Flash column chromatography (FC) was carried out using 3×15 cm column packed with alumina or silica gel. The solvent systems used in various chromatographic techniques are reported in each experimental. Elemental analyses were performed using a Varian 240-C elemental analyser.

Synthesis of starting cyclohexanols :

Cyclohexanols **3** and **4** were obtained by the addition of cyclohexanone to a molar equivalent of PhCH_2MgCl and PhMgBr , respectively, in dry ether followed by reflux for 1 h and stirring at room temperature for overnight. Decomposition by NH_4Cl aqueous solution followed by extraction, drying (Na_2SO_4), solvent removal and crystallisation from petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60 °C) gave **3** (87%) and **4** (82%) in the form of white crystals having the following properties :

1-Benzylcyclohexanol (3) : m.p. 60 °C (lit.^{4a} m.p. 61–62 °C); IR (KBr) ν_{max} 3380 (s), 3010 (m), 2920 (s), 1595 (m), 1577 (w), 1485 (s), 1420 (s), 1140 (s), 710

(s), 690 (s) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 60 MHz) δ 1.3 (1H, s, OH exchangeable with D_2O), 1.5 (10H, m, C_6H_{10}), 2.7 (2H, s, CH_2) and 7.25 (5H, m, ArH).

1-Phenylcyclohexanol (4) : m.p. 62 °C (lit.^{5a} m.p. 61–62 °C); IR (KBr) ν_{max} 3325 (s), 3050 (m), 2920 (s), 1590 (m), 1480 (m), 1440 (m), 1375 (m), 1250 (m), 1115 (s), 747 (s), 690 (s) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) δ 1.0–1.8 (10H, d, C_6H_{10}), 1.9 (1H, s, OH exchangeable with D_2O) and 7.2–7.5 (5H, m, ArH).

Synthesis of reference samples :

1-Benzylcyclohexene (5) : Heating **3** with anhydrous NaHSO_4 and purification by FC (neutral alumina, *n*-hexane) gave **5** (79%) as pale yellow viscous oil, n_{D}^{25} 1.5397 (lit.⁶ b.p. 114°/10 mm, n_{D}^{25} 1.5331); IR (film) ν_{max} 3105 (m), 2930 (s), 1634 (s), 1614 (s), 1488 (m), 1447 (m), 733 (s), 695 (s) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 90 MHz) δ 1.5 (4H, s, $\text{C}^4\text{H}_2\text{C}^5\text{H}_2$), 1.9 (4H, apparent d, C^3H_2 , C^6H_2), 3.1 (2H, s, PhCH_2), 6.15 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, CH) and 7 (5H, s, ArH); MS m/z (%) 172 (M^+ , 13.9), 129 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{C}_3\text{H}_7$, 15.8), 91 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{C}_6\text{H}_9 - \text{H}$, 100), 77 (26.8), 55 (16.7).

2,3-Benzobicyclo[3.3.1]nona-2-ene (8) : Preparation as reported⁶ and purification by FC (neutral alumina, *n*-hexane) gave **8** (77%) as pale yellow oil : n_{D}^{25} 1.5562 (lit.⁶ b.p. 125–126°/10 mm, n_{D}^{25} 1.5523); IR (film) ν_{max} 3025 (s), 2850 (s), 1634 (s), 1614 (s), 1485 (s), 1447 (s), 733 (m), 695 (s) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 90 MHz) δ 1.2–3.2 (12H, br m, unresolved non ArH) and 6.8–7.3 (4H, m, ArH); MS m/z (%), 172 (M^+ , 32.2), 129 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{C}_3\text{H}_7$, 5.8), 91 (100), 81 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{PhCH}_2$, 52.2), 67 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{PhCH}_2 - \text{CH}_2$, 9.3), 39 (6.5).

Friedel-Crafts alkylations and reactions :

General procedure : The standard procedures, described in our previous papers of this series, were essentially followed^{1–3}.

Alkylation of benzene with 1-benzylcyclohexanol (3) in the presence of $\text{AlCl}_3/\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2$ catalyst : A solution of **3** (0.57 g, 0.003 mol) in benzene (2.34 g, 0.03 mol) was added slowly to the $\text{AlCl}_3/\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2$ complex formed in the reaction flask from AlCl_3 (0.48 g, 0.0036 mol) and CH_3NO_2 (2.19 g, 0.036 mol). After complete addition, the reaction mixture was stirred at RT for 2 h and processed as usual to yield 0.52 g (91%) of crude reddish viscous oil. Purification by FC (neutral alumina, benzene) gave 0.5 g (86%) of clean yellow viscous oil : n_{D}^{25} 1.5631, TLC (*n*-hexane/benzene, 8 : 2) showed two components.

GC/MS confirmed the presence of two products (21 and 79%) showing parent M^+ peaks at m/z 172 and 250

corresponding to molecular formulas $C_{13}H_{16}$ and $C_{19}H_{22}$, respectively. Column chromatographic separation (neutral alumina, *n*-hexane/AcOEt, 9.5 : 0.5) of 0.5 g of the latter mixture gave two oily fractions : one (0.08 g) whose analytical data were identical in all respects with those of authentic **8** and another (0.32 g) whose forthcoming analytical data confirmed it to be cyclohexyldiphenylmethane (**10**) : (Found : C, 91.03; H, 8.7. $C_{19}H_{22}$ requires : C, 91.2; H, 8.8%); IR (film) ν_{max} 3040 (s), 2925 (s), 1600 (s), 1487 (s), 1440 (s), 1345 (m), 1260 (m), 1015 (s), 740 (s), 692 (s) cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 90 MHz) δ 1.3–1.6 (10H, br s, C_5H_{10}), 2.5 (1H, m, *J* 6 Hz, C_5H_{10} -CH), 3.35 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, $(Ph)_2CH$) and 7.05 (10H, s, ArH); MS *m/z* (%), 250 (M^+ , 9.1), 167 (M^+ - C_6H_{11} , 100), 91 ($PhCH_2$, 3.4), 8.3 (1.7), 55 (3.3), 41 (2.4).

Alkylation of benzene with 1-benzylcyclohexanol (3) in the presence of 85% H_2SO_4 catalyst : A solution of **3** (0.57 g, 0.003 mol) in benzene (2.34 g, 0.03 mol) was added dropwise to 85% H_2SO_4 catalyst (0.71 ml) and the reaction mixture was left to stir for 2 h at room temperature. Treatment as usual gave 0.53 g (93%) of crude yellowish oil. Purification by FC (silica gel, benzene) afforded 0.52 g (91%) of clear yellowish oil : n_D^{25} 1.5360. GC/MS data showed the presence of five components, two isomers with parent M^+ peaks at *m/z* 172 (corresponding to molecular formula $C_{13}H_{16}$) and three isomers with parent M^+ peaks at 250 (corresponding to molecular formula $C_{19}H_{22}$). Based on comparison with authentic samples, the first two isomers were shown to be **5** (47.4%) and **8** (8%). The other three isomers were found, on the basis of both theoretical considerations and practical observations especially, GC/MS data, to be the following : (a) **10** (21.47%); (b) 1-cyclopentyl-1,2-diphenylethane **12** (17.69%) : MS *m/z* (%) 250 (M^+ , 16.3), 180 (M^+ - C_5H_{10} , 100), 159 (M^+ - $PhCH_2$, 8.2), 91 (20.2), 81 (3.5) and (c) 1-benzyl-1-phenylcyclohexene **13** (3.52%) : MS *m/z* (%) 250 (M^+ , 97.3), 159 (M^+ - $PhCH_2$, 45.7), 91 (100), 81 (13.8).

Treatment of 1-benzylcyclohexanol (3) with $AlCl_3/CH_3NO_2$ catalyst in petroleum ether solvent : A solution of **3** (0.57 g, 0.003 mol) in petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°, 10 ml) was added dropwise to $AlCl_3/CH_3NO_2$ catalyst formed in the reaction flask from anhydrous $AlCl_3$ (0.48 g, 0.0036 mol) and CH_3NO_2 (2.2 g, 0.036 mol). The reaction mixture was stirred for 1.5 h at RT and treated as above to give 0.5 g (87%) of reddish viscous oil which on purification by FC [neutral alumina, petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80 °C)] afforded 0.46 g (80.7%) of pale yellow viscous oil. TLC and GC/MS analysis showed

the product to be a mixture of **5** (25.6%), **8** (62.3%) and a dimer of **5** (10.6%). This dimer whose exact structure was not yet disclosed gave the following MS data : MS *m/z* (%) 344 (M^+ , 27.4), 261 (M^+ - C_6H_{11} , 100), 252 (M^+ - $PhCH_2$ -H, 28.6), 172 (M^+ - C_6H_9 - $PhCH_2$, 17), 91 (44.6), 82 (14.4), 55 (16.2).

Attempted alkylation of benzene with 1-phenylcyclohexanol (4) :

(a) **In the presence of $AlCl_3/CH_3NO_2$ catalyst** : A solution of **4** (0.528 g, 0.003 mol) in dry benzene (2.34 g, 0.03 mol) was added to $AlCl_3/CH_3NO_2$ catalyst formed in the reaction flask from $AlCl_3$ (0.48 g, 0.0036 mol) and CH_3NO_2 (2.19 g, 0.036 mol). The mixture was stirred for 2 h at RT and treated as usual to give 0.51 g (96.6%) of crude which solidified on standing. Crystallisation from *n*-hexane-chloroform (7 : 3) mixture provided 0.4 g (81.4%) of pure faint yellow solid m.p. 127 °C dec. This product discharged the colour of $KMnO_4$ -acetone solution and gave benzoic acid on oxidation with conc. HNO_3 . It also showed the following elemental and spectral data : (Found : C, 90.83; H, 9.07. $C_{24}H_{28}$ Calcd. for : C, 91.13; H, 8.86%); IR (KBr) ν_{max} 3050 (s), 2910 (s), 1590 (s, olefinic double bond), 1480 (s), 1440 (s), 1070 (m), 1030 (m), 745 (s), 690 (s) cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 90 MHz) δ 0.9–2.8 (18H, m, unresolved aliphatic) and 7.0–7.5 (10H, m, ArH); MS *m/z* (%) 316 (M^+ , 51.6), 239 (M^+ - C_6H_5 , 0.7), 183 (22.3), 159 (2.3), 115 (9.7), 91 (16.4), 82 (0.7), 54 (0.9), 28 (100). These data all together added to theoretical considerations, suggested the product to be 1-(1-phenylcyclohexyl)-2-phenylcyclohexene (**17**).

(b) **In the presence of H_2SO_4 catalyst** : A solution of 1-phenylcyclohexanol (0.7 g, 0.004 mol) in dry benzene (3.12 g, 0.04 mol) was added dropwise to 85% H_2SO_4 (1 ml) and the reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h at RT. Treatment as usual gave 0.6 g (84%) of solid which was shown to be identical with **17** obtained above.

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